

Research Article

i-AqadQuest

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Abstract: *The rapid expansion of the Islamic banking sector, projected to reach \$7.7 trillion by 2033, has intensified the need for accessible educational tools to enhance understanding of complex Shariah-compliant financial contracts. Traditional learning methods such as textbooks and lectures often prove ineffective in engaging learners or equipping them with practical knowledge. To bridge this gap, i-AqadQuest was developed as an interactive, gamified platform aimed at simplifying Islamic banking concepts for a wide audience—including students, industry practitioners, and the general public. Built on the ZEP Quiz platform, i-AqadQuest transforms learning into a fun, game-based experience through engaging visuals, customizable avatars, interactive quizzes, and real-time feedback. Players explore a virtual environment where they answer questions to progress, receiving instant corrections to reinforce learning. The platform promotes higher engagement, better retention, and practical understanding of Islamic financial principles. It also includes leaderboards to foster a competitive and motivating learning environment. The tool is accessible across devices, free of charge, and requires no registration, making it ideal for both individual and classroom use. The innovation not only boosts financial literacy among the public but also provides a flexible, self-paced learning tool for professionals to stay current with evolving industry standards. i-AqadQuest holds strong commercialization potential, especially in educational institutions, financial training programs, and community outreach initiatives. Future development may include mobile app integration, expanded content, and advanced features to further enhance user experience and broaden reach.*

Keywords: Islamic Banking; Islamic Contracts; Islamic Finance; Gamification; Tertiary Education.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The Islamic banking industry is undergoing rapid growth. According to GlobeNewswire, the market grew from \$7.16 billion in 2023 to \$7.99 billion in 2024. It also forecasts growth of \$3.4 trillion by 2027 and \$7.7 trillion by 2033 (GlobeNewswire, 2025). The outcome indicated the demand for jobs and education opportunities to the public.

As Islamic banking grows globally, there is a rising demand for effective, accessible ways to understand its complex contracts and concepts. Traditional learning methods, like textbooks and lectures, often fail to engage students and professionals. Meanwhile, the public remains largely unaware of *Shariah*-compliant finance products.

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT & SOLUTION

Islamic banking contracts and concepts are often complex and difficult to understand due to technical jargon and complicated concepts. Traditional learning methods, like textbooks and lectures, can be disengaging for students, also making it hard for them to apply knowledge in real-world situations.

Practitioners also face challenges in keeping up with evolving standards and often lack flexible, accessible learning tools. Meanwhile, the public interested in *Shariah*-compliant finance has limited resources to understand these contracts. *Shariah*-compliant implies adhering to *Shariah* principles. In the context of Islamic financial transactions, this means that all financial transactions must be in line with Islamic law and commercial transaction norms (Engku Ali, E.R.A., 2013). i-AqadQuest addresses these issues by offering an engaging, interactive, and accessible way to learn Islamic banking contracts.

One of the innovative ideas in solving the problem is through i-AqadQuest. i-AqadQuest was created to bridge this gap by offering an interactive, gamified platform that makes learning Islamic banking contracts and concepts fun, engaging, and accessible to a wide audience, from students to industry professionals as well as the public.

3. METHOD & MATERIAL

i-AqadQuest is an interactive, quiz-based game developed using the ZEP Quiz platform (ZEP, n.d.). It is designed to help users learn and master Islamic banking contracts and concepts in a fun and engaging way. ZEP Quiz is user-friendly, as it is free of charge, no sign-up required, and experience is accessible on multiple devices, making it ideal for classroom or individual use. Below are the steps on the using of the i-AqadQuest:

Table 1. Steps to use i-AqadQuest

<p>1.</p>		<p>To get started, users can click on the link that has been shared, scan the QR code or enter the entry code on the ZEP Quiz platform to enter the game. Users are not necessary to log in into their account to enter the game.</p>
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<p>2.</p>		<p>Once the players enter the game, the map of the game “i-AqadQuest” will show up on their screen. This is where they will spawn as the starting point.</p>
<p>3.</p>		<p>On the “Profile” button, players can decorate their avatar and nickname to their likings.</p>
<p>4.</p>		<p>The game starts after the players have turned into animals. To get back into their own self/avatar, the players have to answer all the 20 questions of Islamic contracts by walking into the giant carrots.</p>
<p>5.</p>		<p>The game then begins with a quiz consisting of multiple-choice questions related to the topic. Players answer each question by selecting the most appropriate option. They have to answer the question to get across the giant carrots.</p>
<p>6.</p>		<p>If they choose the correct answer, they can proceed to another question.</p>

<p>7.</p>		<p>If the players choose the wrong answer, they still can proceed to the next question. The game will then show the correct answer. As players progress through the quiz, they must remove the obstacle to get to the finish line.</p>																														
<p>8.</p>		<p>After they finish answering all the 20 questions given, they will transform back into their avatar and their ranking will be shown.</p>																														
<p>9.</p>	<table border="1" data-bbox="359 1041 973 1131"> <tr> <td>1</td><td>2</td><td>3</td><td>4</td><td>5</td><td>6</td><td>7</td><td>8</td><td>9</td><td>10</td> </tr> <tr> <td>X</td><td>O</td><td>O</td><td>O</td><td>X</td><td>O</td><td>X</td><td>O</td><td>O</td><td>O</td> </tr> <tr> <td>O</td><td>X</td><td>O</td><td>X</td><td>O</td><td>O</td><td>O</td><td>X</td><td>O</td><td>O</td> </tr> </table> <p>Question 1 Multiple Choice What is Mubadalah in the context of Islamic contracts? Submitted answer: A contract for safekeeping</p>	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	X	O	O	O	X	O	X	O	O	O	O	X	O	X	O	O	O	X	O	O	<p>The players can see their overall progress to keep track of which area that they have to improve on. The game also features leaderboards, where players can compare their scores with others, adding a competitive element to keep engagement high.</p>
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10																							
X	O	O	O	X	O	X	O	O	O																							
O	X	O	X	O	O	O	X	O	O																							

4. FINDINGS

4.1 Impact of Innovation

i-AqadQuest transforms how Islamic banking contracts and concepts are learned, making it engaging and accessible for students, professionals, and the general public. For students, it turns complex concepts into interactive, real-world scenarios, enhancing retention and application. Students learn through joy and fun. Professionals gain a flexible, self-paced tool to stay updated and continuously improve their knowledge. For the public, i-AqadQuest simplifies Shariah-compliant finance, increasing financial literacy and empowering individuals to make informed decisions. Overall, it fosters a more knowledgeable and financially literate society.

4.2 Commercialization of Innovation

i-AqadQuest can be commercialized by targeting students, practitioners and the public as an engaging educational tool. For students, it simplifies learning complex Islamic finance concepts through interactive simulations. Practitioners can use it for practical training and skill refreshment. The public benefits by gaining accessible knowledge about halal finance and ethical banking. This combination of education and entertainment makes the game appealing for schools, financial

institutions, and community groups, helping spread awareness and understanding of Islamic banking in a fun, practical way. This innovation has the potential to be transformed into an application that can be installed on the phone. Where the users are easily able to access the information and refresh their knowledge on the Islamic banking contracts and concepts. There will be an improvement on the product and more information to be included in the future.

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, i-AqadQuest represents a significant step forward in making Islamic banking education more engaging, accessible, and effective. By leveraging gamification and interactive technology, it successfully addresses the limitations of traditional learning methods, offering a dynamic platform that caters to diverse audiences. With its user-friendly design, broad accessibility, and potential for further expansion, i-AqadQuest is well-positioned to become a key tool in promoting Shariah-compliant financial literacy and supporting the continued growth of the Islamic banking sector.

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